

Frequency-dependent squeezing experiment at TAMA

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Abstract

Earth-based gravitational-wave detectors will be limited by quantum noise in a large part of their spectrum. The most promising technique to achieve a broadband reduction of such noise is the injection of a frequency-dependent squeezed vacuum state through the output port of the detector. Such a state is characterized by a squeezing ellipse tilted according to frequency, thanks to a reflection off a properly detuned Fabry-Perot optical cavity named filter cavity. In this work we present the first evidence of frequency-dependent squeezing production using 300m long filter cavity.

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1 Introduction

Gravitational wave (GW) detectors are the most sensitive displacement sensors on earth: so sensitive that they made possible the first GW detection in September 2015 [1]. The largest GW detectors realized up to now are KAGRA [2], Advanced LIGO (aLIGO) [3] and Advanced Virgo (AdV) [4]. After the first GW detection, many others followed, and that was possible mainly due to the several upgrades that were implemented. Among the many noises that limit the GW detector sensitivity, a fundamental one is the quantum noise. This noise can be understood as the sum of two different contributions: the shot noise coming from the photon counting noise at the photodiode and the radiation pressure noise, due to the momentum exchange between photons and mirrors. The shot noise

is currently the main limiting noise in the high frequency region of the GW detectors' sensitivity. It is expected that soon the radiation pressure noise will be the main limiting source in the low-frequency region, so that the quantum noise will soon set the limit of the entire sensitivity band of GW detectors. The impact of the quantum noise on the total GW sensitivity is even more severe in the case of KAGRA, with respect to aLIGO and AdV.

KAGRA is an underground GW detector operating at cryogenic temperature, currently under commissioning in Japan. Thanks to these two features, the associated noises (namely the seismic noise and the coating thermal noise) will be reduced, having the quantum noise to dominate entirely the detection bandwidth. The most promising technique to achieve a broadband reduction of the quantum noise is the injection of a frequency-dependent squeezed vacuum state through the output port of the GW detector, where the squeeze angle is rotated as a function of frequency. The technique to generate such a vacuum state is based on having a squeezed vacuum state to be reflected off a suitable Fabry-Perot optical cavity, known as filter cavity.

The use of frequency-independent squeezing has been adopted by AdV and aLIGO during the current observation run (O3) in order to limit the impact of quantum noise in the high frequency region of the detection bandwidth [5, 6]. Before the next observation run, both AdV and aLIGO plan to install hundred-meter long filter cavities to produce and inject into the interferometer frequency-dependent squeezing.

A 300m filter cavity prototype is being developed at the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ), using the vacuum system and the seismic isolation system originally built for the TAMA interferometer. The goal of the experiment is to demonstrate frequency-dependent squeezing, with a squeeze angle rotation below 100 Hz, in the region where the rotation is needed for AdV, aLIGO and KAGRA. The experiment is in its final stages: the frequency-independent squeezed light source construction is finished and the commissioning is ongoing (6.1dB of squeezing achieved so far starting from about 10Hz), the filter cavity has been completely characterized and the injection of squeezing into the filter cavity has been started.

In the following we will describe the experimental setup first, then present the frequency-independent squeezing (FIS) and frequency-dependent squeezing (FDS) measurements. We will conclude with some future prospects for this experiment and the implementation of FDS in GW detectors.

2 Experimental setup

The experimental setup is sketched in Fig.1. The experiment consists of three main parts: the in-air optical bench where the frequency-independent squeezing is produced, the in-vacuum injection telescope and the 300m long filter cavity, also in vacuum. Each portion is described in further detail below.

Filter cavity

The filter cavity is hosted in the South arm of the former TAMA interferometer. It consists of two fused silica mirrors with high reflective dielectric coating. Each mirror is suspended using a double stage pendulum suspension and each mirror is equipped with four magnets and a coil driver system which is used to align the mirror and to damp the mechanical resonances of the suspension. The error signal used for the latter is provided by optical lever signals that monitor the position of each suspended mirror. In the case of the filter cavity mirror, optical levers monitor pitch, yaw and length

Figure 1: Sketch of the experimental setup for the production of frequency-dependent squeezing being carried on at NAOJ in the facility of the former TAMA interferometer. The experiment can be divided into three main part: the 300m long filter cavity (red shaded area), the injection telescope (yellow shaded area) and the in-air bench (turquoise shaded area). The sketch is not to scale.

degrees of freedom. The entire FC is in high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar) in order to avoid acoustic coupling and residual gas scattering. In order to control the resonant condition of the FC, not only the squeezed vacuum field but also a green field is injected into it and the Pound-Drever-Hall signal is obtained from the latter.

One of the most important requirement for the filter cavity is the level of round-trip losses. This parameter directly impacts the maximum level of achievable frequency-dependent squeezing, and among the many other degradation processes, it is expected to be one of the most dominant. Reduction of round-trip losses for our filter cavity has been done as one of the first step of the project, and the results of this study are reported in [7].

The complete characterization of the filter cavity was performed in the last year and the results are compliant with the design values. This study is reported in [8]. In Fig. 2 we report some highlight of the study, in particular the FC round-trip losses measurement (left) and the FDS degradation budget taking into account the measured FC round-trip losses (right). The measured round-trip losses are between between 50 and 90 ppm, values which are compliant with the target value of 60 ppm.

Figure 2: Graphs adapted from [8]. (Left) Summary of the round-trip loss measurements. The scattering of the results may depend on different alignment conditions of the cavity from one day to another. The measurements have been taken on different days over about two months. (Right) Quantum noise relative to coherent vacuum (0 dB), computed taking into account different squeezing degradation mechanisms. The yellow area corresponds to the contribution from filter cavity losses between 50 and 90 ppm.

Injection telescope

The injection telescope system is also in vacuum and occupies the tanks of the former TAMA power recycling mirror (PR) and beamsplitter (BS). The telescope itself consists of two reflective mirrors and has a magnification of ~ 10 . The last of the two telescope mirrors is suspended with the same suspension system used for the FC mirrors. Also the 45deg mirror used to inject the beams into the FC is suspended and controlled using the same type of optical lever system used for the FC mirrors. The vacuum tank also hosts a Faraday isolator on the squeezing path and an harmonic beamsplitter. The latter is used to overlap the squeezing field (IR) with the green control field of the filter cavity, while the Faraday isolator is used to separate the in-going squeezing from the one reflected by the FC.

In-air bench

The in-air bench contains the laser sources, the cavities used to condition the various beams as well as the cavity used to produce frequency-independent squeezing, called OPO (Optical Parametric Oscillator). The design of the bench is similar to the one adopted by GEO600 for the squeezer installed since 2008 on the British-German GW interferometer [9].

More in detail, the main laser source of the bench is a 1064nm laser with a nominal output of 2W. About 1W of IR power is injected into the Second Harmonic Generator (SHG) for the production of the green field (532nm). The SHG is a linear hemilitic cavity with a Lithium Niobate crystal inside. The crystal temperature is controlled by means of a thermistor/peltier system and is fixed to obtain the best phase matching condition for optimal IR to green conversion. The green field is then divided into two: a small fraction of the power goes toward the FC and is used as said before to control the FC resonant condition, while most of the power goes to the OPO to pump the non-linear process that produces FIS. Before reaching the OPO, a Mach-Zehnder interferometer stabilizes the DC level of the green beam. The power-stabilized beam is then sent through a triangular mode-cleaner cavity and finally coupled into the OPO. The OPO itself is a linear hemilitic cavity with a PPKTP (Periodically Poled Potassium Titanyl Phosphate) crystal inside. This cavity is resonant only for 1064nm field. In

order not to spoil the low-frequency of the frequency-independent squeezing (FIS), the cavity length is controlled by means of an additional field injected into the OPO in p polarization (while the squeezing is produced in s polarization). In order to have both the fields simultaneously resonating inside the cavity, the natural crystal birefringence must be compensated by detuning of a proper amount the frequency of the p-polarized beam. The detuning of this field varies according to the OPO operating temperature between few MHz up to approximately 300MHz. Another field injected into the OPO is the so called Coherent Control (CC) field. This field, which is detuned by 7MHz with respect to the main laser field, is used as a tracker of the squeezed field which is a vacuum state without coherent amplitude. Using the CC field it is possible to align and to define the phase relationship of the squeezed field with respect to the other fields of the experiment. Both the CC field and the OPO length control field are provided by two auxiliary lasers which are phase-locked to the main laser. The portion of main laser which is not used to pump the SHG constitutes the local oscillator (LO) field to be used at the homodyne detector.

All the controls of the in-air bench are based custom developed analog electronics, with an analog hierarchical control system which can lock the entire in-air system within few tens of seconds.

3 Squeezing measurements

In this section, FIS and FDS measurement are presented. For the FIS measurement, the squeezed vacuum field, once produced into the OPO, is directly sent to the homodyne detector, while in the case of FDS measurement, the FIS is injected into the FC by means of the injection telescope, then reflected towards the homodyne detector on the in-air bench.

3.1 FIS measurements

Figure 3: First FIS measurement performed by the NAOJ group at the beginning of 2019. This measurement is a zero-span measurement at 200kHz frequency. The squeeze angle is rotated at constant frequency while the relative phase between the squeezed field and the LO is uncontrolled. The squeezing level achieved is approximately 3dB while the anti-squeezing level is between 4-5dB.

The first measurement of FIS was achieved at the beginning of 2019. At that stage, the CC loop for the control of the squeezing angle was not implemented and a zero-span measurement at 200kHz was performed, showing approximately 3dB of squeezing. This initial measurement is in Fig.3.

Figure 4: Recent FIS measurement (August 2019). The black spectrum corresponds to the homodyne measurement of the shot noise reference, the red spectrum represents the measurement of the squeezed quadrature, while the blue one shows the anti-squeezed one. All traces are pieced together from two FFT frequency windows: 10Hz-15.6kHz and 15.6kHz-100kHz. The achieved squeezing level is 5.8 ± 0.2 dB while the anti-squeezing is 15.8 ± 0.2 dB. All the spectra are flat from approximately 20Hz up to 100kHz. Several narrow lines and broadband features are present in both the squeezing and anti-squeezing spectra. While the lines are likely to come from power supply coupling, the structures are likely due to backscattered light. This last will be cured by installing a Faraday isolator between the OPO and the homodyne detector.

After the implementation of CC loops and optimization of optical losses as well as phase noise, the level of squeezing and anti-squeezing achieved is as in Fig.4. The measured squeezing and anti-squeezing level are larger than compared to the initial measurement. Moreover with the CC loops engaged, the phase of the squeezed field and the ellipse orientation can be easily controlled. This allows for a FIS measurements down to approximately 20Hz. Several narrow lines and broadband features are present in both squeezing and anti-squeezing spectra. Such features are not present in the shot noise spectrum. This suggests that the source of those features can be related to backscattered light which is reaching the OPO and contaminating the FIS acting as a seed for the non-linear process. In order to avoid this problem, the installation of a Faraday isolator between the OPO and the homodyne detector is planned in the following months. The unbalance between squeezing and anti-squeezing of this measurements suggests that optical losses and/or phase noise are present in our system. This two are the two main source of degradation of squeezed state.

In order to characterize our system in terms of optical losses and phase noise, squeezing and anti-squeezing spectra had been measured for different green pump power. The results of those

Figure 5: Loss and phase noise characterization of the in-air bench. Each data point represents a squeezing and anti-squeezing measurements for different green pump power. The yellow curve represents the expected behaviour of an ideal system with no losses and no phase noise. The orange curve is the fit of the data. From this fit we get a loss budget of 20.8% and a phase noise budget of 26.3mrad. The purple curve represents what we can expect from our system if we reduce to 0mrad the phase noise. This curve shows us that even without phase noise, the maximum level of squeezing that we can expect given the current level of losses is about 7dB.

measurements are in Fig.5. There is an optimal green pump power for the production of squeezing in our system. This optimal value is approximately 40mW. For higher pump power, the squeezing is degraded due to phase noise. By fitting the data we estimated a loss level of 20.8% and phase noise of 26.3mrad. The target value for the experiment are 10% losses and 10mrad of phase noise. Such values are required in order to achieve 9dB of FIS, before injecting it into the FC.

For what concern the phase noise we understand entirely this noise as coming from CC loops and PLLs residual noise. In order to suppress the phase noise, better actuator for CC loops are being designed: the main limitation of the bandwidth (currently about 2kHz) of those loops come from the mechanical resonances of the mirror-mounted piezoelectric ceramic which serves as optical path phase shifter. The loss budget on the other hand is not fully understood. From other measurements we know that homodyne visibility, photodiode quantum efficiency and propagation losses sum up to approximately 10%. The other part of the loss budget comes from the non optimal escape efficiency of the OPO, which was designed to be less than 5%. Further investigation on this topic will be performed in the following months.

3.2 FDS measurements

In order to produce FDS, a FIS state needs to be injected into the FC. The detuning of the FC defines the frequency at which the FDS rotation happens. The optimal detuning for our experiment is ~ 60 Hz. At the present stage, injecting FIS into the FC heavily contaminates the low-frequency part

Figure 6: FDS measurements with 50kHz detuned FC. The blue spectrum represents a squeezed state that, while crossing the FC resonance undergoes an ellipse rotation and becomes anti-squeezed before going back to the original squeezed state. The orange and yellow curve are FDS state projected on the LO reference at different ellipse orientation angle. This angle is named homodyne (HOM) angle and is 0deg for the blue curve, 130deg for the orange curve and 164deg for the yellow curve. In the LO reference, 0deg represents a squeezed state while 90deg represents an anti-squeezed state. The dashed lines are the theoretical prediction of the spectra according to our semi-analytic model. From these curve we can extract the FDS degradation parameters such as injection/readout losses (33% + 11%), injection/readout mode mismatch (10% + 5%), FC locking accuracy also called residual RMS length fluctuation (5pm) and frequency-independent phase noise (70mrad).

of the spectrum with classical noises and makes FDS measurements below 200Hz almost unfeasible. According to our preliminary measurements, this contamination is due to a combination of excess of phase noise, backscattering noise from the FC and beam pointing fluctuation. All those problems will be soon tackled. However for the present time, we decided to set the FC detuning to high frequency in order to investigate the other parameter of our system and measure FDS even at a non optimal detuning. Since our FIS spectrum has some structure below 10kHz, we choose a detuning frequency of 50kHz. We can set the detuning of the FC by changing the driving frequency of an AOM along the green path.

The result of the FDS measurements with 50kHz detuned FC is shown in Fig.6. In the figure the blue spectrum represents a squeezed states that, while crossing the FC resonance undergoes an ellipse rotation and becomes anti-squeezed before going back to the original squeezed state. The orange and yellow spectra are state with a mixture of squeezing and anti-squeezing, or to say in a different way, squeezing ellipse with a different initial orientation with respect to the LO reference. For all the three measurements, the rotation of the ellipse while crossing the FC resonance is evident. On top of the data, theoretical curves are superposed with dashed line of the same color of the data. From the comparison between data and theoretical curve we can obtain several parameter of our system, in particular optical losses (divided into injection losses, i.e. the losses due to the propagation from OPO to FC, and the readout losses, i.e. the losses coming from the optical path between the FC and the homodyne detector), phase noise, mode matching parameters and FC locking accuracy and round-trip

losses can be estimated. According to the current measurements, the main limiting parameters are the injection and detection losses, currently estimated as $\sim 30\%$ and $\sim 10\%$. Such losses are much larger than the $5\% + 5\%$ injection/readout losses planned in [7].

4 Conclusions

In this document, the current status of the frequency-dependent squeezing production experiment being done at NAOJ is presented. Fig.4 shows the current status of the frequency-independent squeezing measurements, highlighting very flat squeezing and anti-squeezing spectra down to approximately 20Hz. Fig.6 represents the first measurement of frequency-dependent squeezing produced with a 300m long filter cavity and gives great amount of information about the degradation processes that can limit frequency-dependent squeezing production.

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